

Beyond the Switch

Can Lighting Control Provide More Than Illumination?

Jon Mason * Dirk Engelen *

** Philips Research, Eindhoven, The Netherlands,
jon.mason@philips.com dirk.v.engelen@philips.com*

Abstract: In this paper a user interaction design project is described where a tangible interface is used to control the lighting in a hotel room. The aim was to design a user interface (UI) that could be used easily by all hotel guests, regardless of their language or origin, to control the increasing number of LED luminaires that in the future may become more common place in a hotel room. The design UI was a tangible interface since they are often more intuitive to use and by tapping into a guest's desire to keep items from the room such as the mini bottles of shampoo, it is predicted that this UI could also facilitate brand loyalty by reminding the guest of their stay. This UI was prototyped and installed in the ExperienceLab at Philips Research Eindhoven and was evaluated by professional hoteliers in order to obtain their feedback regarding the business viability of the concept. The desirability of the UI was evaluated during the Dutch Design Week by the general public in an uncontrolled setting. While 271 visitors experienced the UI only 20 visitors left comments which was the disadvantage of such an uncontrolled test, nevertheless, those few comments did indicate a positive reaction towards the design and use of the UI.

Key words: *Hotel Room, Lighting, User Interfaces, Loyalty.*

1. Introduction

In this paper we take you on the journey through a design project to design and test a new and unconventional form of hotel room UI that can support and enhance a guest's stay and could perhaps make them more brand loyal. Since 2007 a team at Philips Research has been exploring the hotel domain with the intention of identifying new product opportunities for Philips (for this paper the term 'product' includes systems and services as well as tangible devices). Within the hotel domain, looking after people (their guests) is their main business, aiming to provide a positive experience and a good night's sleep. The team began by understanding and learning about the hotel domain and this followed with the conception of many new product ideas. A selection of these ideas were developed further into experience prototypes and integrated into the Hospitality Area of the ExperienceLab. The ExperienceLab is a collection of realistic environments where researchers can install their prototypes and observe people experiencing them for the first time in a safe and controlled environment. The Hospitality Area was designed to represent a small but perfectly formed hotel, including all the features of an ExperienceLab, such as video and audio observation systems and service corridors to hide equipment. Using the ExperienceLab we were able to see firsthand what a hotel room of the future may be like with a variety of

new products that help to enhance and support the time spent in a hotel. We were also able to experience the potential confusion that could arise from these additional products especially with regard to how they may be controlled. Control had not been overlooked by the team, in fact ambient intelligent systems for the hotel room were also part of the research project, but little time had originally been spent on new control solutions that were closer to the market. As a consequence a project was started to design and test a new form of user interaction for the hotel room that could help a guest to control some of the new products that may appear in a hotel room in the near future, such as LED lighting, new types of luminaire (for example a lamp that could help a guest to relax) or products that can help a guest fall asleep more easily.

2. Understanding the Hotel Domain of Today and Tomorrow

Design and creativity literature, on how people design and develop new products generally begin with understanding the domain for which the new product is intended [1-2]: a user centered design approach. This project was no different; literature was searched, hotels were visited, guests observed and invited to focus groups to discuss their experiences of past hotel visits. A brief outline of the current state (2008-2009) of the hotel domain is given below followed by an insight into what the future may hold.

2.1. Hotels Today

Along with many other industries the hotel domain has also suffered during the worldwide recession of 2009 [3]. They too had to cut costs, close hotels and rework their brand identities in order to fill their hotel rooms. The guests, who themselves and their employer were also hit by the recession, were also having to make choices whether or not to travel at all and if so how they can do so most efficiently. If they were to travel they selected their modes of travel and accommodation very carefully. Hotels were now competing for not only fewer guests but more discerning guests who want value [4]. Some of the options were to follow the no frills airline strategy and build a whole new type of hotel or focus on providing enhanced experiences. Hotel chains also simplified their brands and worked hard to increase brand loyalty among their guests in order to ensure a steady turnover [5]. Energy saving became vitally important for more reasons than saving the environment and ways to save money without affecting or reducing the overall hotel experience were of interest to them. Hotels also face some constant issues such as the theft of devices from the hotel rooms with guests trying to walk away with lamps, alarm clocks and even televisions. New products aimed at the hotel domain would have to address these issues if they were to stand a chance of success.

2.2. Hotels Tomorrow

For Philips Research, it is the hotels of tomorrow that show the greatest promise since new innovations from research could take two to three years to enter the market place and thus an understanding of future trends is vitally important. Using trends reports from The Future Laboratory [4] as well as speaking with hotel chains it is possible to identify trends that can guide the design thinking.

It is expected that for many people, staying in a hotel will go beyond simply looking for a place to sleep, but it will be seen as an opportunity to expand their minds and take in new experiences. Some smaller boutique and design hotels are providing more meaningful and thought provoking products in their rooms such as

contemporary interior décor designed by famous artists or designers, iMacs, computer games consoles, enhanced lighting, exquisite in-room menus, breathtaking views and services from staff that go above and beyond expectations. Through the provision of more products and services in a room, hotels can differentiate from the competition. Additional predictions also foresee the increase in technology in the hotel room [Fraunhofer InHaus Visit] [6-7]; however, hotels must ensure that this technology is simple to use and reliable otherwise guests could find it annoying and this may lower their impression of the brand [4].

Energy saving for financial and environmental considerations is a current and future trend that is likely to endure as guests become more conscious of their impact on the environment. Already many hotels across the globe are encountering increasing numbers of guests who base their hotel selection on a hotel's eco credentials and not just price or location [8]. LED lighting is becoming the default choice for hotels due to their low energy consumption. They can also be controlled more precisely than previous lamp types (e.g. incandescent or CFL) and can provide additional and new features, such as colour, dynamic effects and form new types of luminaires such as those can provide breathing patterns to aid relaxation. Such possibilities reinforce the likelihood that LEDs will appear in hotel rooms of the future.

The Future Laboratory also predicted the rise of is the Bleisure (sic) guest: one who likes to mix their business and leisure time [4]. This type of guest will potentially pose a great change for the hotel domain since the traditional business or leisure hotel categories will have to mix and combine offerings to appeal to this new group. For example, the current weekday and weekend demarcations will become blurred as these guests may take holiday during the week instead. The hotel room will have to provide good working conditions as well as a playful and relaxing leisure feel and the use of LED lighting and ambiances could facilitate hotels in achieving this.

3. The User Interaction Problem

The control of the LED lighting, the lighting ambiances and potentially additional features, such as relaxation lamps or fall-a-sleep functions became the focus of the project since controlling these new features represents a real and increasing need in the hotel room of the future. Furthermore, it is difficult to identify precisely who the guest is, for it is in a guest's nature to travel and thus they can come from anywhere in the world with their own language and culture; it is not always certain who will be staying in a hotel room and using the products in there. Hotel chains try to tailor their brand to appeal to certain guest types but ultimately anyone can still walk through the doors of a hotel and ask to stay the night. With regard to the foreseen Bleisure (sic) guest type, even the typical business and leisure demarcations are disappearing; therefore, when designing products for the hotel it may be wiser to design for the extreme case.

The control of LED lighting has of course been addressed by other companies and a number of solutions are currently available. The most common UI approach incorporates the usual switches, dials or sliders that have traditionally been used older lighting systems; such a solution is acceptable when only a few lamps or luminaires need controlling or there are only a few lighting ambiances to select from. The guest will be able to remember which button controls what, for a low number of features. When the number of features in a room increase, it

will be harder to control these using only switches. The CitizenM hotel chain provides rooms with four lighting ambiances and remotely controlled heating and blinds [9] and these features are controlled using a handheld touch screen device. The advantage of this is that a number of layers of control can be hidden and revealed when needed; however, this technology is not always suited for all guest types, e.g. the elderly or partially sighted.

4. The Globe UI

Armed with our understanding of the hotel domain and their guests, ideas were generated for ways of controlling numerous LED lighting ambiances. To solve this problem typical design methods were used to drive the ideation and development (i.e. sketching, modeling, brainstorming) and our solution was a user interface we called the Globe UI. The Globe UI has two key facets. The first is a method that could bridge barriers such as language and help guests from all over the world understand and learn how to control the lighting. The second facet is the tangible interface embodiment; this is an unusual choice for use in the hotel domain considering the issue they have with theft, but this will be explained below.

4.1. Globe Metaphor

For this UI to be used easily, by those from all over the world, it was clear that language and even icons were not suitable. Both language and icons are not necessarily universally understood and can cause confusion [10]. A clear example of this is the trouble a colleague had trying to flush the toilet in his Japanese hotel room; he was unable to read the text on the switches that controlled a plethora of features. Furthermore, many motorists around the world can become confused at the strange icons and images on foreign road signage; this is potentially the same for icons used in hotel rooms.

To solve this the team explored the notion of metaphors [11] and using the general knowledge a community may have, for example, the desktop metaphor is widely used to facilitate the organization of an operating system. Galitz found that metaphors based on the real world were understood more easily [12] and this insight helped to direct the exploration. The community we were designing for were travelers of the world and the general knowledge they could all have is a basic understanding of the different climates around the globe. It is known that the north and south poles of the globe are cold. It is also known that as you move towards the equator the temperature increases. Employing these facts, it is possible to provide a link to lighting ambiances with warm lighting ambiances found towards the centre of a globe and colder lighting ambiances found towards the poles. The detail of the ambience can then be increased by linking colours and dynamics to each country. For example, Iceland would be cool with a hint of blue where as Italy would be warmer and have more terracotta. This analogy between lighting and climate became the basis for the Globe UI concept.

The advantage of this model for selecting lighting ambiances over more traditional activity based models is that there is more flexibility and room for making an error. When using an activity based model a guest may select a 'work' themed ambience, but if this ambience is not suited to how that guest likes to work in a hotel room (e.g. on the bed, at the desk, in the comfy chair) then the hotel has failed to understand him or her. Using the seasons is one way of circumnavigating this issue but not all nations have the same set of seasons. Whereas, with a

climate based model the guest may not agree with some of the representational ambiances of a particular country, but this does not dictate to them how they should work, relax or use the hotel room. The guest is allowed to explore and select an ambience in which they could work, relax or watch TV in. Moreover, this selection can be made without the need for keywords or icons.

Additional aspects of a hotel room can also be controlled seamlessly using this Globe UI concept. For example, the temperature of the room could also be controlled in relation to the climate of the country selected, with Spain setting a warmer temperature than Norway. A guest may also indicate to the system in the room where they are from using the Globe UI and thus the system can tailor the room to suit their needs, such as placing the television channels associated with their country at the top of the menu list. This could be an interesting method for providing services to guests from different countries and cultures.

4.2. Tangible Interface

For the UI to work a guest must be able to make the link between the Globe UI and controlling the lighting. From our interviews and focus groups it became clear that guests would like to have some light on when they enter a hotel room so they can see into the room and that it is safe. This can be achieved via automatic sensor based lighting, a switch by the door or using a keycard slot to provide power and lighting for the room on entry. Thereafter, the Globe UI must attract the guest into moving the pieces over the board and thus via trial and error they would learn how to use the interface. Tangible interfaces have been considered to be a more intuitive means of human computer interaction [13] for they can provide a more multi-sensorial experience [14].

Embodying the Globe UI concept using a tangible interface clearly undermines the knowledge collected regarding the issue hotels have with theft. Providing a hotel with a control interface that has pieces that can be stolen was not considered the ideal solution at first. User centered design is about understanding and designing for users, stakeholders and their needs; and sometimes, when visiting a hotel it seems that some people need, or feel that it is their right, to take the shampoo, soap and other items from the room. Would it be so bad if guests were to keep the tangible pieces from the Globe UI? If these tangible pieces were attractive enough, guests may take them and keep them at home as a memento of their stay [15] and these pieces may remind them to book that hotel chain again in the future. Famous designers could be commissioned to design some of the pieces and if tagging technology is used a guest's favourite setting could be linked to that piece so they can use it on a return visit to instantly re-set the hotel room to how they like it best. These views were suppositions at this point in the project but a prototype and presentation to hotel managers and guests revealed the potential.

4.4. Construction of the Globe UI Prototype

The Globe UI was built as a working prototype for the hotel room in the Hospitality Area of the ExperienceLab. The original intention was to use a touch sensitive sphere over which a picture of the earth could be placed. When people placed a marker on a particular country an ambience relating to that country would be rendered in the hotel room. Unfortunately, such a prototype would have taken too long to build and thus the alternative was to use a two dimensional mat that could detect a variety of pawns via their individual magnetic field strength. The form of the pawns represented a small and friendly space rocket that could travel around the globe to

different landing sites. Due to the size limitation of the mat and the location of the areas that could sense the pawns' presence only a part of Europe could be represented and implemented for this prototype. Task lighting was also included in the control interface and these were represented by miniature desk lamps (figure 1).

Figure 1. Image of the Globe UI.

The ambiances that would represent each country were based on image searches for each location via the internet. The general colour essence of each country was rendered using the LED luminaires available in the hotel room (figure 2); this was a difficult and highly subjective task. More advanced systems could use algorithms to mine the internet for images and use them to determine the colours that should be rendered in the room. Furthermore, such light settings need not be static and can change over time to suit the seasons of the country or to link to topical events that may be taking place there.

Figure 2. Image of the hotel room in which the Globe UI was installed.

5. Desirability and Viability of the Globe UI

With reference to Tim Brown's framework on selecting and determining the potential of concepts [16] we considered the feasibility, viability and desirability of the Globe UI. The feasibility of a concept refers to the technology required to realize such an idea. This was not an issue for the Globe UI since readily available technology was used and linked seamlessly to a Pharos Lighting System which many industrial locations use for their lighting management. The viability of a concept refers to the business potential and the desirability to the acceptance of the concept to the user; with reference to the Globe UI these are explained below.

5.1. Viability

The viability of a concept refers to how well it fits into the world of business and how it can potentially facilitate a company in increasing its turnover, saving costs, building on its brand identity and so forth. For concepts such as the Globe UI, determining its precise and potential viability is difficult at such an early phase in the design and research cycle. The ExperienceLab is a useful tool for this process since the installation of a realistic prototype can provide an early indication of how complex it may be to install such a system in the real world. For the case of the Globe UI the installation was simple, requiring only a small control unit (currently a laptop) running a piece of code which provided a communication bridge between the input detection of the tangible pieces and the Pharos Lighting System. Provided a lighting (control) system was installed in the hotel room the Globe UI could be connected without major changes to the infrastructure; thus increasing the business viability of the concept.

The ExperienceLab also enabled the team to test the viability of the Globe UI by inviting hotel managers to experience the concept in a realistic environment; therefore, they do not have to rely on their own imagination and they can evaluate more easily how such a concept could work for them. Representatives from two major hotel chains visited the lab to review the Globe UI. The representatives consisted of local hotel managers, managers from head office and one hotel technician. They were invited to the hotel room and were introduced to the Globe UI. Instantly they were keen to try the UI and they explored the different ambiances of the countries and turned on and off the different task lights. From this moment the discussion, and even an ideation session, regarding the viability of such a product for a hotel room ensued. The hoteliers' comments were recorded via hand written notes and a questionnaire containing quantitative and qualitative questions. The key insights from these two sessions are discussed below.

5.2.1 Simplifying the hotel room

The representatives from both of the hotel chains acknowledged the existence of the transition to LED based lighting in the hotel room, for energy saving reasons as well as for providing an enhanced experience. Each of the hotel chains already have test rooms that includes LED lighting that can provide the guest with a selection of lighting ambiances. They understood the problem of having to control the LED lighting in meaningful way that guests would understand. The analogy of using a country's climate was appreciated for its simplicity at being easy to understand quickly and for its relevance to hotels and travel. Other ideas that were appreciated were to use the Globe UI to control other aspects of the hotel room such as the heating and air conditioning; for example, selecting Iceland could activate a bright and white ambiance and also lower the temperature in the room. The

ambience could also be influenced by real time aspects such as the time of day or the weather at the selected location.

5.2.2 Increasing the potential for brand loyalty

The essence of a tangible interface is of course the physical pieces that provide the user with a means to control a system. Within moments of experiencing the Globe UI the hotel representatives noted that these tangible pieces would be stolen from the rooms. Theft is a big issue within the hotel domain with guests helping themselves to small and large items from the hotel rooms and these pieces would be no exception. This response was not a surprise and was expected by the team. A discussion was then held regarding the viability of allowing the guests to keep the tangible aspects of the Globe UI. With minor modifications it would be possible for each tangible piece to be linked to a guest's profile and thus personalized services could be offered. For example, a guest could save their room ambience preferences and when they return to a hotel within the chain they can simply set their new hotel room to how they like it. The hotel could also provide additional features for the guest via the Globe UI such as the relaxation luminaires. Furthermore, if the guest takes the tangible pawn, because they like it they may display the piece on their desk or in their home and when come to book another trip the visual reminder may encourage them to use that hotel chain again (figure 3).

Figure 3. Part of the Globe UI sitting on a guest's desk in the office.

In combination with a good experience in using the Globe UI and the chance to keep a part of it as a memento, this could build satisfaction with the stay and that is a necessary aspect for increasing the loyalty of a guest [5]. Some guests may begin to collect the different pawns and keep them as souvenirs which in an ambient intelligent environment provide the guest with digitally stored memories from the hotel stay [15]. This notion increased the appeal of this concept to the hotel representatives on the condition that the pawns could be supplied as cheaply as the bottles of shampoo or bars of soap (10 to 20 Euro cents).

The conclusion from the hotel representatives' visits was that the analogy of using the globe/climate for the control of the lighting, and potentially other aspects of a hotel room, was considered to be suitable for this domain due to its simplicity. The potential viability of this concept was increased further by the fact that the pawns could be used as personal UI and as souvenirs; this may promote customer loyalty through personalization of a room's features or as little piece of the hotel that can travel with them to remind them of their stay. This could place hotel room UI into a new and higher realm than a simple light switch or touch screen.

5.2. Desirability

The desirability of a concept depends on how well it resonates with real people; essentially this refers to whether or not people see a need for this in their lives, be it for functional or hedonistic reasons. To test the potential desirability of the Globe UI an opportunity presented itself in the form of the Dutch Design Week 2009. During this week the ExperienceLab was opened to the general public for the first time in its history, allowing anyone to visit and be taken on a tour to experience a selection of the concepts. The decision was made to include the Globe UI in the tours so that the visitors could use and experience it for themselves. This method of testing a concept was unlike a typical research study where participants from a particular sample group are recruited, provided with precise activities to follow and are perhaps video recorded and asked to complete a questionnaire. In contrast, during the design week, we had no control over who visited the ExperienceLab or how they interacted with the concepts which is similar to a hotel having little control over who stays in their rooms. This is similar to a study by Peltonen et al. who placed an interactive wall in a city centre and observed how the public used it [17].

During the week 271 visitors, from students to pensioners, passed through the ExperienceLab and experienced seven different concepts, including the Globe UI. The visitors were invited to leave their comments regarding the seven concepts on post-it notes and in total 96 notes were posted. Twenty of the 96 notes posted provided comments regarding the Globe UI. Of these twenty comments, seven were positive with visitors commenting on how fun it would be to have this in a hotel room and to be able to control more than just the lights with such a system. Two visitors were negatively disposed towards the concept, regarding it as too childish and unnecessary. The remaining 11 comments were constructive with the visitors providing their ideas on how to improve the concept further. Examples included: wall mounting the board; interactive tangible pieces; turning the UI into a game with two people; and caution on controlling too many features with one piece. The desirability of the Globe UI, therefore, appeared to be high with the negative comments being outnumbered by the positive. The number of additional ideas and suggestions for improvement was useful and provided an indication of how to make the concept more desirable in future iterations.

This particular method of testing the desirability of a concept may not be scientifically honorable but it was an efficient way of exposing the concept to a large number of people in a short space of time and for obtaining an initial idea of its potential desirability.

6. Discussion

The Globe UI was a solution designed to solve a problem that has not yet materialized in the world. The control of multiple LED luminaires, lighting ambiances and other features in a hotel room is only just beginning

to appear in a few lead hotels. As this becomes more prolific more inventive UI is needed as we identified from our own experience in the ExperienceLab. This enabled us to experience feature creep in a hotel room and ways to address this issue were investigated.

The design of the Globe UI had two key parts. Using the general knowledge present in travelers from all over the world should help to make the UI more understandable without reverting to the use of language or icons. From the visitors to the Dutch Design Week we found that this model was clear, understandable and was accepted by those who saw it. However, the majority of the visitors were from The Netherlands and thus do not represent a broad hotel guest population, nevertheless this does provide an early indication that this may be a promising direction to pursue. The hotel managers also liked the idea for it fitted with the notion of travel and exploration and the opportunity to reinforce their branding.

The embodiment of the Globe UI was a tangible interface and it was known by the team that this was potentially a contentious decision with regard to the pieces being stolen from the hotel room. Should the team have taken the literature and data collected from the hotel industry as absolute, this tangible interaction means would have been dismissed in favour of a more permanent solution. By rationalizing the fears behind an issue it was possible to explore new areas and show users a new perspective on the current situation. From discussions with the hotel managers it became clear that by designing for theft and allowing guests to take the pawns these may act as a memento for their stay and encourage or remind them to revisit the hotel. The pawn may also be personal to the guest and be used on subsequent return visits to set their favourite preferences in the room. This idea can potentially turn hotel room UI from an expense to a potential marketing tool that could help to increase guest appeal, experience and turnover. According to the hotel managers this could be a possible use of a UI within the hotel domain but the cost of the pawns must be low (10 to 20 euro cents) for the concept to remain viable from a business perspective.

Tangible interfaces have been found in the past to be an enjoyable method of controlling devices and in particular their ability to draw people in and encourage them to engage in the activity [18] and this Globe UI was no exception, attracting the hotel managers and visitors towards it so they could try it for themselves. They all wanted to explore the different locations to see what the lighting ambience would be like for different countries. Interestingly, as predicted, when the light rendering did not match a person's idea of what it should be, they found it funny and moved on to select another country; such discrepancies did not appear to upset or annoy them.

The evaluation of the Globe UI has thus far been unorthodox but it has been insightful. The hotelier studies provided important feedback on how such a concept could be integrated into a hotel and how else a UI could be used to enhance their branding and even their brand loyalty. Additional studies with hoteliers from other hotel brands are required to substantiate these findings. The advantage of collecting data during the Dutch Design Week was that it exposed the Globe UI to a large population of people (n=271), with little control over how they experienced the concept and thus had a degree of similarity to a real hotel situation for they too have little control over who wishes to stay in their rooms. The comments collected on the post-it notes provided an indication of the desirability of this concept and ideas for how it could be improved. Unfortunately the response rate for

providing comments was very low with only 20 of the 271 visitors providing a comment on the Globe UI; therefore, a degree of control is advisable, for example, enforce the writing of comments or ask them to complete a concise questionnaire of one or two questions only.

7. Conclusions

From this project we have identified some new insights into alternative ways that user interaction systems can be used within the hotel domain and how they may potentially go beyond the traditional light switch and become a key differentiator and even a tool for marketing a hotel's brand. The two key features of the Globe UI, the link to the climate of the world and the use of tangible control pieces, were also positively received by the hoteliers and visitors to the Dutch Design Week. From a user centered design perspective issues considered by the population to be undesirable (e.g. theft) may turn out to be an opportunity for new ideas and change; therefore, information from users should not always be accepted as absolute.

Using an event such as the Dutch Design Week to evaluate a concept ensured that many people experienced it but in an uncontrolled way. Should this approach be used in the future, means to control the feedback mechanism (i.e. writing comments on a post-it note or questionnaire) should be controlled and enforced more rigorously than was done in this project. Nevertheless, the comments that were provided by the visitors were useful for not only determining the concept's potential desirability but also for generating new ideas and suggestions for improvement.

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